
**PROBLEMS OF OBJECTIVE DEFINITION, DESCRIPTION AND
DETERMINATION OF THE TERM IN MODERN TERMINOLOGY**

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Annotation.

In the article, debates on the definition and description of the term in modern terminology, lexeme, special lexicon, term, term, nomen, sectoral lexicon (professionalism) concepts, term token, candidate term, hybrid term, terminoid, prototerm, nomen, nomenclature, professional argotism, the concepts of professional jargon, slangism, and quasi-terms are discussed. The study describes the definition of a scientific term, which is a word or phrase that expresses a specific concept related to science. These terms are characterized by specific signs such as systematicity, descriptive functions, monosemanticity and lack of emotional content.

Key words.

lexeme, special lexicon, term, nomen, lexical field, professionalism, term token, candidate term, hybrid term, terminoid, prototerm, nomen, nomenclature, professional argotisms, professional jargonism, slangism, quasi-term

Modern terminology has become one of the most serious areas of linguistics undergoing the most changes in today's globalization era. [3.213] At the moment, both in world linguistics and in Uzbek linguistics, a large part of the researches on lexicology is made up of works devoted to terminology. Although its emergence and study has a long history, until today the debates about its unity, definition and description of the term have not stopped, the concepts of lexeme, special lexicon, term, nomen, sectoral lexicon (professionalism) have not been clearly defined. The lack of a single point of view regarding the structural-grammatical composition of

terms - simple, compound, double, repeated, compound, abbreviation terms confirms that terminology is the most susceptible field of linguistics to changes in the social, economic, political, cultural life of the country, and develops together with society. New problems of terminology regularly appear on the agenda of linguistics, in particular, the object of terminology is abandoned in traditional ways and approached in the mirror of modern linguistic paradigms - cognitive, social, psychological, semiotic, communicative, pragmatic aspects [8.249], from one language to another with great speed. terminographic formalization of acquired terms, determination of their orthologous form, terminological variation, scientific justification of term-orthograms, tagging of field terms in national corpora, terminology token, candidate term, hybrid term, terminoid, prototerm, nomen, nomenclature, professional argotism, professional jargonism, slangism, quasi-term[6.213], etc., a number of researches are being carried out, which indicates that this field is always developing. One of the main reasons for this is related to the fact that terminology is the field of linguistics that is most susceptible to changes in the social, economic, political, and cultural life of the country. If there is a need to collect and research the terms of a certain field in a single system and reflect them in dictionaries, it means that the fields that need this dictionary have developed in the country.

The emergence of a need for a terminological dictionary for a specific science or field indicates the development of this field, the development of science and technology in general, and the social, economic, political, and cultural development of the country. This prompts linguists to repeatedly focus on the study of concepts related to special fields - information technology, technology, business, economy, education, medicine, politics, advertising, law, and scientific and technical field in general.

The dramatic increase in the role of science and technology in the life of society has led to the emergence of new terms and field terms. This process was so accelerated that even the representatives of the field had a number of problems related to their assimilation, understanding, and application. The increase in the sources of term formation is not only derived terms, but also the morphological-derivative construction, structural composition, selection of a single orthologous form of terms of their own layer, which are formed on the basis of internal possibilities, clarifying the issues of polysemy and synonymy in terms, in general, today, regulating terms, interpreting them in dictionaries. problem led to the country being considered as one of the priority areas of socio-economic and cultural development.

Uzbek lexicography and terminology were ordered to "introduce scientifically based new words and terms, create Uzbek alternatives to modern terms and ensure their uniform use"[25]. In order to ensure the implementation of the Decree No. PF-5850 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 21, 2019 "On measures to fundamentally increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as a state language", the Terminology Commission was established under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Introduction of new scientifically based words and terms into official use before the Commission; to ensure that the concepts and terms in the drafts of regulatory legal documents are used in a uniform form and correctly in accordance with the meaning adopted in the legislative documents in such a way as to exclude the possibility of different interpretations; ensuring compliance with the rules and norms of the literary language, as well as legal, technical and other special regulations in the projects of regulatory legal documents; edit the inconsistencies that may arise due to the rules of other languages without harming the norms of regulatory legal documents; studying the legal problems of introducing new terms entering the Uzbek language into legal documents and applying them in practice, determining the directions of development of legal regulation of relations in this field[26] and other tasks were set.

The development of science has increased the demand for tools that provide explanations and spelling of terms. As a result, countless printed and electronic dictionaries, offline (direct) and online (remote) programs, dictionaries, information banks appeared in all languages of the world.

"Annotated Dictionary of Technological Terms", "Annotated Dictionary of Biology Terms, Terms and Concepts", "Annotated Dictionary of Psychological Terms and Terms" on the idum.uz website, which has been operating since 2012 for the Uzbek segment only. "Annotated dictionary of terms related to computer science", "Annotated dictionary of terms and concepts related to economics", "Annotated dictionary of terms used in physics", "Annotated dictionary of terms and concepts related to mathematics", "Brief explanatory dictionary of diseases", "Explanation of terms used in the history of Uzbekistan", "Annotated dictionary of terms used in the science of literature", "Annotated dictionary of terms related to attestation", "Annotated dictionary of terms used in lesson development"[The fact that more than twenty electronic dictionaries such as 35.2] are placed and each of them is referred to by more than one hundred users in a day confirms how much demand there is for the dictionary of industry terms today. But how perfect are these tools, what linguistic principles are based on the formation of their

vocabulary - which criteria led the selection of terms, lexicographic interpretation of terms - semanticization? These questions are still open.

The term has attracted the attention of linguists and has been at the center of linguistic research since the earliest times, as a unit that fully reflects the state of the country's scientific and technological processes, the scale of development. E. Wuster, E. Dreizen, H. Felber, J. K. Seiger, B. Bruno, F. H. Lang, R. Temmermen in world linguistics, G. O. Vinokur, A. in Russian linguistics in the formation and development of the theory of traditional terminology. A. Reformatsky, V. V. Vinogradov, B. N. Golovin, R. Yu. Kobrin, D. S. Lotte, F. P. Sorokoletov, V. G. Gak, S. V. Grinev-Grinevich, V. P. Danilenko, A. V. Superenskaya, L. Yu. Buyanova, V. M. Leychik, T. L. Kandelaki [10.254], in Uzbek linguistics S. Ibrohimov, S. F. Akobirov, U. Tursun, A. Khojiev . Madvaliev, A. Husanov, Z. Mirahmedova, A. Kasimov, Q. Sapaev [17.46] and others have made a great contribution.

In scientific literature, the term appears in different meanings. For example, science and technology terms, art, culture terms, sports, craft terms, socio-political, literary terms, etc. In particular, in Russian linguistics, N.V. Khrushevsky's work entitled " Очерк науки о языке " published in Kazan in 1883 defines the term as " разряды слов, имеющих номинативную функцию" (category of words performing a nominative function) [19.296]. In V.I. Dal's dictionary published in 1880-1882, the term is explained as " выражение, слово, речение, название вещи или приёма, условное выражение " (phrase, word, sentence, name of thing or event, conditional expression) [24.4] . Almost simultaneously with this dictionary - in the encyclopedic dictionary of F.A. Brockhaus and I.A. Efron, published in 1890-1907, there is a similar phrase "слово, которому соответствует определенное понятие, или изолированное, или входящее в состав суждения или умозаключения" (known a concept is defined as a word that fits, is isolated, or is included in a judgment or conclusion). Specificity to a certain field, scientificity is emphasized as its characteristic[8.524]. O. Vinokur also defines the term as "не особые слова, а только слова в особой функции" (not a special word, only a word in a special function)[12.3-10]. According to V.V. Vinogradov, a word performs a nominative or definitive function [10.12-13], in the dictionary of O.S. Akhmanova, it is emphasized that a word or a combination expresses a specific concept, it becomes scientific and is considered a term [7.]

S. Ulman considers all words in the language to be terms and distinguishes two categories of them: 1) special terms; 2) general terms. He intended to include specific words in the first category, and "vague general words" in the second category[27.36-37]. In particular, in logic, any word representing a set of

descriptions related to a specific object is considered a term. That is, from the point of view of logic, a word expressing any specific concept in the language can be a term [18.656].

While A.S. Gerd focuses on the fact that the term is a special word or combination that reflects the essence of certain concepts that arose at a certain stage of the development of science[13.1-4], V.G. Gak focuses on defining the term and performing a special function within lexical units[13.68-71]. A somewhat perfect study of the term is associated with the name of F.P. Sorokoletov in the 70s of the last century. He, like O. Vinokur, considers the term as a word with a special function: "A term is not a special word, it is only a word with a special function." By special function, he meant the naming of a concept, thing, or event related to a specific field. That is, the term does not mean the lexical meaning associated with the usual concept of this word [24.384].

The modern online dictionary *Wiktionary* explains 17 meanings of the term. Main meaning 1 "That which limits the scope of something; border, had, obstacle / That which limits the extent of anything; limit, extremity, bound, boundary, terminus" style. The following meanings are explained in relation to the field. For example, in geometry, mathematics, logic, astrology, art, etc., interpretation is given according to the context of the field.

In modern English, the term directly represents the meaning of the word term - limit, limitation. Middle English terme, Old French terme, Latin terminus border, barrier, limit, end; in the Middle Ages in Latin it meant time, period, word, covenant and other meanings. The term was also used in this sense in Old English[31].

The opinions of M. T. Cabre, M. K. Homme, G. Rondo, S. Pavel[4.vol16] and others on the interpretation of the term in modern terminology are worthy of attention. In particular, the works of M. T. Cabre Castellvi dedicated to the research of this field serve as a methodological basis for terminological research in modern linguistics.

The well-known representative of world terminology, Spanish linguist, Professor María Teresa Cabre Castellvi, in her article entitled "Theories of Terminology: Their Description, Principles and Interpretation", clarifies the reasons why the theory of terminology has caused the most debates in the last decade, why this topic arouses interest in many people.

The author of the article relates the main reason why modern terminology has not yet come to a single agreement on the definition and description of the term with Wüster's theory. "I will first discuss the theory developed by a Wüster and

clarify the motivations behind his model. I will then explain why 's t Wüster heory was accepted unchallenged for so long. Only then will it become clear why the terminology has been the cause of so much debate and controversy in recent times, both from a traditional point of view and from a modern point of view" [2.163].

So, what was 's term Wüster inological theory based on, what did this theory prevent from giving an objective definition of the term in modern terminology?

Eugen Wüster (1898-1977), an Austrian interlinguist and the founder of terminology theory, was originally an engineer. At the age of 15, he became interested in the Esperanto language and soon became known as a translator and author of various monographs and articles on Esperanto terminology and lexicography.[29] The interaction of languages in the conditions of multilingualism, the analysis of the processes of creation and operation of international artificial languages, various aspects of interlingual communication, in particular, the department of linguistics, which studies international languages as a means of communication - the field of Esperantology, and during his engineering activities, he developed the international principles of standardization of terminology and developed the modern information society. contributes greatly to the creation. E Wüster's interest in terminology was mainly related to two cases. Worcester was not only an engineer and entrepreneur, but also an influential Esperantist. As a professional engineer, he saw language as a tool that should be adapted to the needs of any user. As an Esperantist, he believed that it was possible to form and even invent languages. Therefore, Wüster's terminological theory has an onomasiological character. He emphasizes that the basis of the term is not a name, but an expression of a concept. According to Wüster, a term does not need to acquire a semantic (conceptual) essence in order to express a certain concept. It should be accepted with the meaning explained in the dictionaries.[5.55-58]

Nevertheless, in recent years, it is noted that "all attempts of linguists to create a single scientifically based definition of the concept of "term" have failed." In this study, we did not set the main goal of clarifying the issues of definition and description of terms in linguistics. Since our main goal is to clarify the place of distance education terms in the modern terminological system based on English and Uzbek language materials, we studied the debates surrounding the issue of the main unit of terminology in linguistics without moving away from the research object.

Therefore, the term means a word or a combination of words that expresses a special concept related to science, which is characterized by the emergence of specific signs such as belonging to a certain system (systematicity), possessing

nominative and definitive (describing) functions, tendency to monosemanticity, freedom from emotions.

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